

The Integrity of Reverse Supply Chain using Blockchain Technology

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade or so, there has been a rapid development in e-commerce services. Digitization has led to a focus on the user experience. Online retail has moved from multichannel to omnichannel to provide various e-commerce services. Today it has become very easy for users to buy products and services and also return these products if not found satisfactory. A service like return and exchange is a standard part of any digital e-commerce platform today if they want to remain in business. For this to work out a very efficient and solid reverse supply chain (RSC) is necessary. However, over the recent years, the RSC has become a favorite target and has been attacked multiple times elevating reputation risk for companies. A lot of Manpower and Training is required to manage this situation. This paper proposes a solution using blockchain technology (BT) to prevent fraudulent activity and benefit the producer-consumer ecosystem. BT can streamline and reduce the efforts to ensure the integrity of the supply chain by sharing accurate product information to all parties without the fear of any data manipulation.

Keywords: - Digitization, e-commerce, reverse supply chain (RSC), fraudulent, blockchain technology (BT),

1. INTRODUCTION

Technology and e-commerce have made it convenient for consumers can quickly see, compare, and purchase products that they need. It has become very convenient for users to look for a product they need and quickly place an order with just a click of a button. To ensure a good customer experience and quick delivery of these products, producers and marketers rely on supply chain management and many other activities related to ensuring good service. At the heart of this is the logistics. Logistics has come a long way from traditional activities. Many companies are integrating multiple channels of delivering products. Retailing through the mode of online virtual or offline entities helps consumers in the swift purchase of goods they need. The scope of channels is broadened by the omnichannel world, by assimilating returns, order frequency, exchanges, customer-retail channel interactions, acquisition, and the revenue impact of customers [1]. Many a time when the product is purchased, it must be returned or exchanged for not meeting the requirement of the consumer or being defective. The process of returning the product is called the reverse supply chain. However, this has led to the development of fraudulent activities which are hard to detect sometime. If left unchecked, it can lead to financial losses, poor customer experience, and damage to the reputation of the produce. One of the most prevalent activities is return fraud [2]. Return fraud is when the consumer returns goods back to the retailer or sales channel knowing that it violates the company or legal policy. Many times, a counterfeit product is also returned by making it look like an authentic purchase. The case is worse for mobile and home appliance products. These products are usually fast-moving and relatively high-value products making them a good target for return fraud [3].

In a recent study, it was found that the chance of exchange fraud using fake or stolen is as high as 40% for mobile phones and 90% for larger household appliances. The total estimate of losses is at a minimum \$220 million. As per the study, 82% of mass-market retailers are aware of the return fraud issues. A study on clothing returns shows that 50% of all returns are fraudulent. In North America, almost 8% of returns can be classified as fraudulent and with

ineffective return policies. The traditional methods to identify and prevent fraud are very manual and unfortunately have many problems and are limited by headcount, training, and scaling [4]. Most sophisticated return frauds can lead to depression in retailers' profits. Too demanding return policies can make genuine return customers reluctant. On the other hand, a very lenient return policy can lead to the misemployment of the policy. To counter this problem there are many technology-based solutions exist. For example, image recognition, fraud detection using analytics, etc. A lot of changes could also be done to the whole return process which requires more and more accurate information about the customer and products to be captured through online channels or at POS. Analytics software can then be used to perform historical analysis to identify a fraudulent pattern to alert the retailers or distributors to detect fraud. But these techniques are post-event techniques and are expensive. These reasons give us the motivation to provide a solution using blockchain in reverse logistics to return fraud. This study puts forward the unchangeable feature of the blockchain which captures a unique digital footprint at every transaction process and prevents return fraud in retail. These footprints are shielded from fraud and forgery using smart contracts on the blockchain and consumers, retailers, and other stakeholders are protected [5].

2. CONCEPT OF SUPPLY CHAIN AND ITS FEATURES

2.1 Reverse Supply Chain

The reverse supply chain process deals with managing returns and repurchasing surplus goods and materials, it is also responsible for managing any leases or refurbishments. The reverse logistics process may vary across different industries, and there exist different economic incentives and drivers for improving the reverse supply chain [5].

As an example, in the beverage industry, empty containers are often brought back to the manufacturer. The manufacturer reuses empty containers and captures value. This is a humongous task as it requires careful planning and execution to collect, load, transport, and clean the containers. As the construction industry adopts more sustainable practices to reduce waste, the cost can be reduced by using reverse logistics. In the construction industry, as they try to adopt more sustainable ways of doing business, there are many opportunities to recycle salvaged material and move it to the new site [6].

For the food industry, the challenges are a bit different; they are responsible for returning packaging material and pallets. They are also many a times required to dispose of contaminated food or take back the items which have not been sold.

2.2 Forward and reverse supply chain process

I am positioning this solution for high-value transactions primarily consumer electronics, apparel, etc. as it is evident that the majority of the fraudulent returns happen in this transaction for two reasons. Firstly, because the transaction value can be high, and secondly, these items are easily movable. The below figure shows the typical sales cycle and a return transaction happens in the following manner. Manufactures produces the item -The items are sold to the distributor-The distributor sells to the retailer-Retailer makes a final sale to consumers [6].

During Return transaction cycle

- 1) Customer realizes that the product is defective or non-usable or doesn't meet the requirements as claimed in the advertisement
- 2) Customer goes to the retailer and submits the product with receipt
- 3) Retailers takes the product and exchanges the same for newer product or provides refund
- 4) Retailers than send the product through distributor; Distributor replaces the product or refunds the retailer

A distributor collects the returned and sends it to the factory; Factory accepts the product and replaces the product for distributor or pays them. Once the item is sent back to the manufacturer, it could further go through different paths. As an example, the item could be resold, or it could be repaired and resold or it could be disposed off or it could be salvaged for reusable components and then disposed off. So basically, either the product will enter recirculation or product may have to be disposed off [6].

However, return fraud in this process could create significant issues. A fraud product may be accepted by the retailer and distributor but may not be accepted by the factory. A counterfeit or defective product may reenter the supply chain. A stolen product may enter the supply-chain. These issues can lead to significant loss for the retailer and distributors and may hamper the reputation of the company.

Fig-1: Forward and reverse supply chain process

2.3 Returns

In a process of product return in retail, a customer sends a product back to the retailer that he had purchased previously and in turn receives an exchange for another item, a refund, or store points. Many retailers accept returns if the customer is able to show a receipt as proof of purchase, and also other certain conditions are met as per the policy. The conditions could be that packaging needs to be preserved or if receipts are missing then some other identification needs to be shown or returns can be done within a stipulated time from the purchase date. Many times instead of giving cash back to the customer only exchange or store credits are given. Some merchants may charge a fee for restocking a defective item [7].

Retailers are usually not bound to accept returns. But in many places laws are such that retailers require posting their return policy that is distinctly noticeable to the customer prior to purchase. In specific countries, like Australia for example, consumer rights help consumers to get a full refund under some specific situations. For example, a situation where sales is done using false claims, defective goods, misleading claims and where conditions of sale are hidden [7].

Customers may want to return merchandise for numerous reasons, like a change of one's mind, receiving a faulty product, or a purchase of the wrong product, dissatisfaction. In case of cloths, it might be a wrong fitting. Sometimes, the manufacture may recall a product and as a mandate merchandise needs to come back to the store. Also gifts receipts are given some time and the person may exchange it some items of comparable value.

2.4 Return fraud

Return fraud is a type of online scam where an item is purchased from a retail store and is returned to get money back. It is the way of defrauding a retail store via the return policies of the company. This crime has been committed by consumers or fraudsters in various ways. For example, the consumer may return stolen merchandise to get a cash back, steal receipts to enable an return or use someone else's receipt to return a merchandise purchased from a stores. As per recent study, in return fraud and policy abuse the retail industry has incurred a loss of about \$24 billion per annum, which is about 8% of the total returns. In 2020, 6% out of 10% of the return transactions were fraudulent, which costs about \$25.3 billion (<https://fraud.net/d/return-fraud/>). As retail moves from brick and mortar to online, merchants report that, there is a rise by 38% in online buying, return in-store purchases, and a rise by 29% in fraudulent return among these transactions. More, 21% of fraudulent cases were due to the transactions done without receipt. This influences merchants to raise prices to make up for the losses which in turn reduces and affects the customer experience [7].

The following are types of Return frauds [8][9]

Return of stolen merchandise – Stealing and returning merchandise for full price refund

Receipt Fraud – Manipulating receipts to return merchandise for gain.

Employee Fraud – The stolen goods are returned for full price with the help of employees. This is insider fraud.

Price Switching – Labels are changed the on the merchandize and later returned at a higher price than what was initially purchased for.

Price Arbitrage – Returning the cheaper item in place of similar-looking but differently priced labeled goods.

Switch Fraud – A perfectly working item is purchased and a defective or damaged item is returned.

Bricking – Purchasing an item, removing its components and then returning the item as faulty.

Cross Retail Return – An item is exchanged at another retailer for cash, store credit, or a similar, higher-priced item at another retailer.

Open Box Fraud – This is like price-switching where “open-box” store policies are misused.

Wardrobing – Buying item for a short-term use and returning it by saying it doesn’t match the requirement.

3. INTRODUCTION TO BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchain records information in such a way that it makes it difficult or next to impossible to change, or hack, or manipulate the system. A blockchain is a digital shared ledger of transactions. It is duplicated and spread across the network of computer systems on the blockchain network. Each block in the chain contains multiple transactions, and every new transaction is a recorded and added automatically to every participant’s ledger to create redundancy. Multiple participants manage this decentralized database which is known as Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT). Blockchain is a type of DLT in which an immutable cryptographic signature called a hash-key is used to record transactions. The hash algorithm has a property that even a slightest change in the input creates a completely different key and is one way in nature [11].

Fig-2: The Properties of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)

Fig-3: How does the Transaction get into the Blockchain

Fig-4: Links between previous blocks

Reference: [13]

3.1 Block chain-based solution for preventing return fraud

In a block chain-based solution every transaction will be captured and stored on a block chain. This block chain will be a shared immutable ledger to which every party will have access to. The product will have a QR code which can be scanned by any person with mobile phone to know the product status. It will have all the important information about the product like name, Model number, Year of manufacture, place of manufacture, status (Working/Broken/Defective etc.), reason for return, product color, weight, owned by, warranty etc [14].

- 1) The moment the product is returned, it will be tagged with the place, time, and the reason it is returned.
- 2) At this return stage, the product will also be validated for its authenticity.
- 3) This will trigger an event in which the distributor and the manufacturer will know precisely know why and when and where the return is coming from.
- 4) At every stage in the reverse supply chain, information is captured, and the status of the product will be updated.
- 5) If the product makes it back to the supply chain, everyone will have a history of the product and the reason for return.
- 6) If the product is refurbished, the status of the product will be changed to refurbish.
- 7) If the product is stolen the product will not be validated on the blockchain.

3.2 Enhancing Blockchain-based solution with smart contract

To take this a step further, the blockchain can be equipped with a smart contract. A smart contract is functionality in the blockchain which can create certain events automatically. As an example, refunds to the different parties, triggering of certain workflows, and things can be executed in a smart contract without human interference. [10]

4. CONCLUSION

Although time and time again people or groups of people will always find a way to commit return fraud, technologies like blockchain will make it very difficult to commit this fraud. Although blockchain technology can handle all the transaction-related frauds, something like employee fraud may not be detected. Technology alone cannot solve the problems of the reverse supply chain. What is required is a strong process and technology combination. Technology is an enabler, but a strong execution is also required to ensure the full potential of that technology. Smart contracts within the blockchain can automate and streamline a lot of reverse supply chain processes and improve the speed at which operations are performed.

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